

ZOOLOGY

SPECIES COMPOSITION AND NUMBER OF RODENT CARRIERS OF THE PLAGUE PATHOGEN IN THE (MOYINKUM DESERT PLAGUE FOCUS IN 2021

Bely D.,

*Head of the laboratory of epizootology of especially dangerous infections
Republican State Institution "Zhambyl Anti-Plague Station" of the Committee of Sanitary and Epidemiologic Control of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Taraz city*

Niyazaliev K.,
zoologist

Republican State Institution "Zhambyl Anti-Plague Station" of the Committee of Sanitary and Epidemiologic Control of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Taraz city

Nurbaev K.,
zoologist

Republican State Institution "Zhambyl Anti-Plague Station" of the Committee of Sanitary and Epidemiologic Control of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Taraz city

Kopkova A.,
zoologist

Republican State Institution "Zhambyl Anti-Plague Station" of the Committee of Sanitary and Epidemiologic Control of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Taraz city

Sayakova Z.

Candidate of Biological Sciences, Senior Scientific Associate

*Republican State Enterprise "Institute of Zoology", Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan,
Almaty city*

Abstract

The work was carried out taking into account the specific epizootic situation of plague in 2020, on the territory where the course of plague among mammals has been observed for more than 40 years, which is a constant potential threat of epidemic of this infection among the population. Taking into account the fact that plague epizootic was detected by bacteriological method during rodent plague testing in spring 2015, and in the fall of the same year local low-intensity plague epizootic was detected by serological method in the tract "Shynyrau kudyk", indicating the continuation of the epizootic, as well as intensive human economic activity in the active Moyinkum desert plague focus, in the spring season of 2021. studies of the state of fauna and rodent abundance in the Western Remnant Landscape-Epizootologic Region (LER) were conducted. During the research period, the territory on the area of 3000 km², which is a part of the Moyinkum desert plague focus, was surveyed. Among rodents, large and small gerbils, yellow gopher and small marmoset were studied, among predators - fox, skogpa, buzzard and harrier. Rodent abundance was low.

Keywords: rodents, natural plague focus, landscape-epizootologic region, carriers of the plague pathogen, great gerbil, small gerbils.

Introduction. The plague epizootic in the study area was detected in spring 2012 at the following points: "Satybaldy" 1 culture of plague was isolated from the greater sandfly and 1 seropositive greater sandfly was detected, "Kadyrbek" 1 culture of plague was isolated from the greater sandfly; "Shynyrau kudyk" 1 seropositive greater sandfly was detected; plague epizootic was detected at the following points: "Satybaldy" ur. "Kadyrbek" 1 culture of plague was isolated from the great sandfly; "Shynyrau kudyk" - 1 seropositive great sandfly was found; the plague epizootic was characterized as local, intensive, occurred on a total area of 300 km² [1]. In the fall of 2012, no epizootic process was registered in this territory.

In spring 2013 local low-intensity epizootic of plague was detected by serologic method in tracts "Kokdala", Baikozha, headquarters Bekmurat, Sadykzhal, Kuzendidala, Suzhal-1. The plague epizootic at all sites was characterized as local, low-intensity and occurred on a total area of 600 km² [1]. From the

fall of 2013 to the fall of 2014, despite the survey of the territory, no plague epizootics were registered.

In spring 2015, the epizootic process was registered by bacteriological method on the area of 500 km² in the tract "Shokai" isolated 5 strains of *Y. pestis* from fleas of the great gerbil burrows of the plague pathogen from the flea of the burrows of the great gerbil *Xenopsylla gerbilli minax*. In the tract "Koizhigit" 1 culture of the plague pathogen was isolated from the suspension of the great gerbil in the tract "Zhaylybek" 1 culture of the plague pathogen was isolated from the red-tailed gerbil and in the tract "Kokdala" 1 culture of the plague pathogen was isolated from the great gerbil, around the settlement "Kishi Kokdala" 1 culture of the plague pathogen was isolated from the flea of the great gerbil burrows: *Xenopsylla gerbilli minax*. The plague epizootic was characterized as local low-intensity. In the fall of 2015, local low-intensity plague epizootic was detected by serological method in Shynyrau kudyk. The plague epizootic at all sites was characterized as

local, low-intensity and flowed over a total area of 100 km² [1]. From 2016 to the fall of 2017, despite the survey of the territory, the plague epizootic was not detected.

In spring 2018, a local low-intensity plague epizootic was detected in the tracts "Satybaldy" (1 seropositive great sandfly was isolated), "Kadyrbek" 2 seropositive great sandflies were isolated; The plague epizootic at all sites was characterized as local, low-intensity and flowed over a total area of 200 km². An inter-epizootic period was observed from fall 2019 to spring 2021.

The main host of the plague pathogen is the great gerbil. Great Sandpiper settlements are mostly sporadic and occur in small groups [2-4]. The density of settlements is very low. Only in the extreme northwest in a relatively small area and in some places in the southeast along the southern edge of the sands, colony density is somewhat higher. Numbers of the Greater Sandpiper in these areas averaged 3.0 individuals per 1 ha, varying from 0.5 to 4.5 individuals per year [5-7]. In addition, the Noon Sandpiper, Grebeschik's Sandpiper and Red-tailed Sandpiper inhabit the area. The Noon Sandpiper dominates among the Small Sandpipers. The abundance of the Yellow Gopher is also low. Other rodents are rare. The vectors are fleas of sandflies, mainly of the Greater Sandpiper [8-9]. According to long-term averages, their number in the habitat of the Greater Sandpiper is 140 specimens per 1 ha, with annual variations from 24 to 535 [10-12].

The purpose of our research was to study the state of the fauna and to conduct an inventory of the number of rodents in the Western Remnant Landscape-Epizootic Area, as well as their natural enemies - predatory animals.

Materials and Methods.

Great Sandpiper was captured from 10-12 rodent colonies. Traps were placed 1.5 km apart. On one colony 2-3 traps were placed, for a more uniform survey of the territory, 1-2 gerbils were captured from each colony on average, after which the traps were moved to colonies that had not been trapped. First of all, the survey was conducted in the vicinity of settlements, by sectors and was aimed at searching for local epizootics in the places of plague pathogen establishment and adjacent areas.

During the spring season of 2021, 500 rodents, including the greater sandfly, were captured.

The population of the greater sandfly was counted using the route-colonial method, while the lesser sandflies and other small rodents were counted using the trap-night method.

The trapping of Greater Red-tailed Sandpipers was carried out with special traps placed at the entrance to the burrows of these rodents. No more than 2 gerbils were captured per colony, after which the traps were moved to other colonies.

Small Sandpipers were counted by placing 100 traps with standard bait (bread moistened with vegetable oil) in a line at 5-meter intervals in the main habitats, as well as traps placed on colonies of large sandpipers.

Counts of Yellow Gophers were carried out on autoroutes (number of sightings per 1 km). Small gopher

tortoises were counted at dusk in the light of car headlights (number of sightings per 1 or 10 km of route).

Numbers of rodents were determined by the trap-night method. When counting in settlements, at least 20% of the total number of objects were surveyed. Small settlements with up to 20 houses were surveyed completely. At the same time with counting the number of rodents, four-legged predators were counted by trapping them in traps placed on colonies of Great Sandpipers.

The number of raptors was judged by the number of birds seen per daylight hours.

To conduct stationary observations of the Greater Sandpiper, 3 fixed points were selected, which most fully reflect the landscape-ecological peculiarity of the surveyed area. The following ecological observations were carried out at the stationary points of permanent record:

- a/ observations of rodent population composition and breeding intensity;
- b/ counting the number of embryos in pregnant females;
- c/ registration of repeated pregnancy and embryo resorption;
- d/ study of multi-year population dynamics of the great gerbil;
- e/ change of colonies, interspecific contacts, rodent mobility, etc.

Results

During the period of work from 28.05.2020 to 16.07.2021 the survey was conducted on the area of - 3000 sq. km². The abundance of Great Sandpiper (*Rhombomys opimus* (Lichtenstein, 1823)) in the whole LER per 1 km² amounted to 228 individuals, with colony occupancy of 37.6 %. Colony density averaged 146 per 1 km². The average number of Greater Sandpipers per colony was 4.6 individuals. The percentage of minor rodents caught in traps was 0 % per 100 l/n.

Counting of the number of the main carrier of the plague pathogen is carried out before the release of young animals. In the study area, 51.8% of animals survived the winter period, which stabilized the number of the main carrier in most parts of the LER.

In general, the number of Great Sandpipers per 1 km² in spring 2021 was 256, with a range of 77 to 384, and 141 in spring 2020, with colony occupancy rates of 37.6 % and 43.6 %, respectively.

During the 2021 summer season, 196 Great Sandpipers were captured in the Western Remnant LER, of which 67 (34.2 %) were sexually mature males and 112 (57.1 %) were sexually mature females. Of the sexually mature females: 35 (31.3 %) were yearlings, 67 (59.8 %) were littered, and only 7 (6.3 %) were pregnant. Young were captured 17 (8.7 %), of which 10 (58.8 %) were young males and 7 (41.2 %) were young females.

The ratio of sexually mature females to males, was 1.7:1. The percentage of females participating in reproduction was 66.1%.

The number of embryos per pregnant female was 2.7, ranging from 1 to 5. The breeding intensity index was 22.

Numbers of the Noon Sandpiper (*Meriones meridianus* (Pallas, 1773)) are generally low in the area. For example, the percentage of their occurrence per 600 l/n was 0% in the LER.

Numbers of Red-tailed Sandpiper (*Meriones libycus* (Lichtenstein, 1823)) are generally low in the area. The percentage of their occurrence per 600 l/n in the LER was - 0.

Numbers of Grebe Sandpiper (*Meriones tamariscinus* (Illiger, 1811)) are generally very low in the area. For example, in the LER the percentage of their occurrence per 500 l/n was - 0%.

In the Western Remnant LER this summer, numbers of Ruffs remain at a low level. No geese were caught in fishing gear. At dusk single animals were encountered on the routes, and 10 Little Ruffs (*Allactaga elater* (Lichtenstein, 1825)) were recorded per 10 km of the auto-route (or 1.0% per 1 km of the route). Their numbers may increase slightly in the fall of 2021.

Numbers of yellow gophers (*Spermophilus fulvus* (Lichtenstein, 1832)) on the territory of the Western Remnant LRR were below average. Gophers were not specifically captured during material sampling.

Three routes were established to record the abundance of yellow gophers:

The total area of these routes was 3 km², 15 yellow gophers were encountered, with an average of 0.15 animals per 1 km².

Numbers of terrestrial predators (weasels, bandages, ferrets) in the area were counted visually and by trapping. Four-legged predators were not specifically captured. Their numbers are still low. A total of 2 Red Foxes (*Vulpes vulpes* (Linnaeus, 1758)) were recorded.

Among raptors, an average of 2 birds were seen per daylight hours, mainly Buzzards (*Buteo rufinus* (Cretzschmar, 1827)). Nests of buzzards contained mainly 2 eggs, but not more than 3 eggs. In addition to Buzzards, Osprey Pandion haliaetus (Linnaeus, 1758), Harrier (*Circus pygargus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) were recorded, approximately 1 - 4 birds of prey per 10 km of the vehicle route.

Weather conditions are characterized according to the data of the weather station located in Oyyk settlement. The winter of 2020-2021 was snowy with rare precipitation in the form of snow (18 days). The winter temperature background was close to the average long-term data and was -8.4. Spring was relatively cool and prolonged.

In the 1st decade of March the temperature background was +4.10 C, in the 2nd decade of the month - 1.10 C. In the 3rd decade of the month and average air temperature amounted to +8.30 C. The average monthly air temperature was +3.80, last year +7.00 C, with a norm of +1.70C. Precipitation in the form of rain fell in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd decade (11 days). Snow cover on the soil surface was recorded until March 20, while last year it was until February 7. The transition from 00°C to above zero temperatures was recorded on March 19 (February 13 last year).

In April, the weather was stable, within multiyear values. Air temperature in the first ten-day period was + 10.70 C, in the second ten-day period + 15.10 C, in the third ten-day period + 16.70C. Precipitation fell in

the form of rain in the second and third ten-day periods of the month (accompanied by strong easterly winds in the first and second ten-day periods). Rare flowering of tulips was observed in the first, second and third ten-day periods of April. Rare flowering of poppies was observed in the third decade of April. The vegetation condition assessment was low due to weak vegetation of ephemerals and ephemeroids. In general, weather conditions in April were favorable for rodent activity.

In May, the weather was stable, moderately warm but windy, with strong easterly winds prevailing. Precipitation fell in the first and second decades of the month (3 times). Air temperature was +21.30 C in the first decade, +23.00 C in the second and +28.40 C in the third. Assessment of vegetation condition was unsatisfactory, ephemerals and ephemeroids vegetated poorly, wormwood and sagebrush grew poorly, meager flowering of poppies continued until the third decade of May.

In general, it can be said that the spring of 2021 was late and drier than the spring of the previous year. The forage base for rodents was insufficient due to weak vegetation of desert vegetation, climatic conditions were satisfactory and sufficient for rodent activity (Table 1).

Thus, the abundance of the Greater Sandpiper here remains below average. Thus, the number of animals in summer of this year was 266 animals per 1 km², with an average colony occupancy rate of 38.2%. The index of intensity of the main carrier remained at the last year's level and amounted to 22. The average number of embryos per pregnant female was 2.7. Taking into account the above-mentioned data, it can be assumed that by the fall of 2021 the number of the greater sandfly in the whole territory under favorable weather and climatic conditions will be higher than last year's data, therefore, the possibility of a local epizootic of plague in the fall of 2021 is not excluded in this territory.

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